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THE PLACE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF AVIATION ENTERPRISES

Oksana Kyrylenko, Valentyna Novak, Mykhailo Podrieza. *«The place of organizational culture in the management system of aviation enterprises».* This scientific article is devoted to the study of the organizational culture of air transport enterprises. Organizational culture defines the values, norms, ideas and practices that shape the way the enterprise functions. A detailed analysis of the organizational culture of air transport enterprises will allow to understand the key factors that affect their efficiency and competitiveness, to determine the place of organizational culture in the management system. In addition, the article offers strategies for the development of organizational culture aimed at improving the performance of air transport enterprises.

Keywords: organizational culture, aviation enterprises, management system, development strategy, leadership.

Оксана Кириленко, Валентина Новак, Михайло Подреза. *«Місце організаційної культури в системі управління авіаційними підприємствами».* Дана наукова стаття присвячена дослідженню організаційної культури авіатранспортних підприємств. Організаційна культура визначає цінності, норми, ідеї та практики, які формують спосіб функціонування підприємства. Детальний аналіз організаційної культури авіатранспортних підприємств дозволить зрозуміти ключові фактори, що впливають на їх ефективність і конкурентоспроможність, визначити місце організаційної культури в системі управління. Крім того, у статті запропоновано стратегії

розвитку організаційної культури, спрямовані на підвищення ефективності діяльності авіатранспортних підприємств.

Ключові слова: організаційна культура, авіапідприємства, система управління, стратегія розвитку, лідерство.

Introduction. In recent years, managers increasingly raise the issue of the need to create a high organizational culture at enterprises, which also has proper scientific justification. The culture formed in organizations has a significant influence on management decisions and, in fact, all processes of the enterprise's functioning. The management of powerful foreign enterprises sees the reasons for success precisely in a high organizational culture, because among the important factors of the effectiveness of personnel functioning, it is the organizational culture that ensures the formation of a set of unique conditions. In many Ukrainian enterprises, the role of organizational culture remains implicit, especially from the point of view of influence on the efficiency of operations. That is why the question of researching the process of organizational culture formation is important for the implementation of the experience of foreign enterprises in the practice of Ukrainian enterprises, the basis of which should be the synthesis of modern scientific provisions.

The formulation of the goals of the article is a generalization of theoretical and practical issues of organizational culture formation and ensuring its positive impact on the effectiveness of the organization's functioning. Based on the set goal, the following tasks are expected to be solved: to systematize the approaches of scientists to the definition of the concept of "organizational culture"; to investigate the development factors and stages of formulating the organizational culture of the enterprise; clarify the key characteristics of the organizational culture that corresponds to the high level; to investigate the influence of organizational culture on the efficiency of the enterprise; summarize the experience of foreign companies and determine the

conditions for its implementation in the practice of Ukrainian companies.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The work of many scientists has been devoted to research on the formation of organizational culture. In their works, the factors and goals of the formation of the organizational culture of industrial enterprises are defined, and the algorithms of the formation of the organizational culture of enterprises of certain industries are given. However, the peculiarities of aviation enterprises during the war and in the post-war economy of Ukraine, which act as factors of influence on organizational culture, have not yet been investigated, which led to the conduct of this study within the framework of the article.

Presenting main material. Organizational culture is one of the most influential elements of organizational management. It can be attributed to the factors of influence on management, since it is based on the ability of managers to communicate correctly with subordinates, to determine under which cooperation the work will be most successful: performed individually by each subordinate or collective performance. Each manager must develop the culture of the enterprise, and for this he must apply methods of assessing the organizational culture in his team, which include questionnaires, conducting exercises, trainings, researching instructions or other documents that explain cultural elements, comparing his own organizational culture with others, more perfect and be able to introduce changes in a timely manner, if necessary. Organizational culture is defined as the conceptual essence of the organization, which determines the general value system of the enterprise [2]. It is subject to regular

changes, which are carried out by introducing innovations into the work of the enterprise.

Thanks to an effectively functioning organizational culture, the enterprise can respond in time and dynamically to any manifestations of the market environment, be a market leader and have high competitiveness. For this purpose, it is necessary to understand the mechanism of formation of the organizational culture of the enterprise, its goals, influencing factors and values. Taking into account the research in the field of organizational culture, it is worth noting that the specifics of the formation of the organizational culture of water transport enterprises have not been considered by scientists before, but it has its own characteristics that should be taken into account when forming it. There is still the question of ensuring the moral and material interest of water transport workers of Ukraine in increasing the efficiency and quality of work, stimulating the continuous labor activity of workers, consolidating the professional staff and its development.

Organizational culture determines the way of life and work in the organization. In the context of air transport companies, organizational culture plays an important role in shaping corporate identity, motivating employees to achieve high standards and providing quality services. This article offers an in-depth analysis of the organizational culture of the world's air transport enterprises, highlights the key factors affecting their effectiveness, and considers development strategies for achieving high results.

Organizational culture is a set of values, ideas, norms, symbols and practices that shape the way the organization functions. It affects the thinking, behavior and interaction of employees. Organizational culture can be visible (symbols, clothing, rituals) and invisible (values, norms, ideas). Components of organizational culture include leadership, communication, management style, cooperation, innovation and other aspects.

Factors influencing the organizational culture of air transport enterprises:

A. Leadership and corporate values. Leadership affects the formation of organizational culture. Quality leadership should contribute to the development of values that support high standards of quality and safety. Leaders must lead by example and encourage employees to self-develop and innovate.

B. Communication and interaction. Effective communication is an important element of organizational culture. Clear communication and openness help build trust and understanding between employees. In addition, it is important to encourage cooperation and interaction between different departments and levels of management.

C. Management style. Management style determines how decisions are made, how resources are allocated, and how control is exercised. A high-quality management style promotes the development of autonomy, stimulates their creativity and initiative. Flexibility and openness in decision-making contribute to rapid response to changes in the aviation industry.

D. Safety and quality culture. In aviation, safety and quality are critical aspects. Organizational culture should contribute to the formation of an uncompromising approach to flight safety and service quality. Ensuring training and conscious compliance with safety regulations and procedures help create a high safety culture in air transport enterprises.

Strategies for the development of the organizational culture of air transport enterprises:

- Attracting and developing talented employees. To develop organizational culture, it is important to attract and develop talented employees. This may include a system of support and career development, educational programs and trainings that contribute to the development of professional skills and leadership qualities.

- Creating a stimulating environment. Creating a stimulating environment is an important aspect of organizational culture

development. This may include establishing reward and recognition mechanisms, encouraging creativity and innovation, encouraging cooperation and collective achievement of goals.

- Definition of clear goals and values. Defining clear goals and values is an important element in the development of organizational culture. It helps direct the efforts of employees, stimulates their independent motivation and focus on achieving common goals.

- Communication and employee engagement. Effective communication and involvement of employees in decision-making processes are important elements of organizational culture development. Openness, transparency and cooperation contribute to the involvement of employees in the formation and improvement of organizational culture.

1. Organizational culture is a key element of the success and competitiveness of air transport enterprises. Leadership, communication, management style, safety and quality culture are important factors that determine organizational culture. Development strategies, such as attracting and developing talent, creating a stimulating environment, defining goals and values, communication and engaging employees, contribute to achieving high performance and developing the organizational culture of air transport enterprises.

2. Leadership in aviation enterprises affects the formation and development of organizational culture. Leadership defines the company's values, vision and mission, and motivates employees to achieve high standards and achieve common goals. Quality leadership contributes to the formation of a holistic organizational culture in which employees feel part of a team, a community, and develop in accordance with common values and norms.

3. Leaders in aviation enterprises have a great influence on the formation of organizational culture by:

4. Setting goals and defining a common vision. Leadership defines strategic goals and directs the enterprise to achieve a common vision. This helps create a common goal and direction for all employees.

5. Creation of corporate values and norms. Leadership establishes corporate values that define standards of behavior and interaction within the organization. This includes ethical principles, responsibility to employees and customers, and a commitment to innovation and improvement.

6. Stimulation and motivation. Leadership stimulates and motivates employees to achieve high results and exceed expectations. This can be done with the help of a system of rewards and recognition, promotion of professional development and expansion of competences of employees.

7. Communication and interaction. Leadership ensures effective communication within the organization. Leaders must be open to feedback, listen to employees, and facilitate interaction between different levels and departments.

8. Example and influence. Leadership sets an example for other employees. Leaders must live up to the values and norms they promote and demonstrate responsible and ethical behavior.

Organizational culture is formed in the process of communication and joint problem solving to achieve the common goal of the founder of the enterprise and a group of like-minded people [4]. As a result of these processes, one's own values, criteria for achieving common goals, rules and norms of behavior, and forms of interaction with the external environment are produced. That is, a necessary condition for the formation and development of organizational culture is the joint activity of people and the presence of a common goal. When forming organizational culture, one must realize that it is necessary to create conditions in which its continuous development will take place.

In order to maintain their positions in the market, organizations need to respond to

changes in the external environment and change their organizational culture accordingly. Adapting to changes, organizational culture creates an internal environment that contributes to the constant process of accumulation, distribution and exchange of knowledge among employees, which prepares the enterprise for possible future changes in the environment [3,5].

The results of the aviation enterprise are related to its organizational culture. Organizational culture occupies a place in the basis of the organization of management of all factors of the company's activity, which seem imperceptible, but are actually the most significant. Thanks to a high organizational culture, the airline company receives results that embody the complex effects presented in the article. At many enterprises, a well-formed or high organizational culture occupies a key place in the management system at the same level as the development strategy. The question of the dependence of the results of the researched enterprises on the key characteristics of the organizational structure requires further research.

Conclusions. So, organizational or corporate culture is a combination of the organization's politics and ideology, its system of priorities, motivation and distribution of power. It characterizes the social values and norms of behavior of its participants, is a basic belief, a standard for norms and patterns of behavior shared by employees of the organization during a certain period of its existence. It is laid in the

subconscious of employees and determines the style of their behavior, forms the unity of the organization. It can also be defined as a formed set of templates, basic values and principles of adaptation of the organization to external changes, which are recognized and accepted by employees, as well as the process of forming relationships among groups of employees in the enterprise. In order to understand the influence of organizational culture on an aviation enterprise, it is necessary to determine the stages of its formation and what processes it affects. Organizational culture is formed either consciously as a result of individual and purposeful actions of leading members or arbitrarily under the influence of social processes arising from the relationships of persons employed in the organization, important events at the enterprise and the stability or dynamics of the external environment. Undoubtedly, when the key development goals were in the area of building up the material and technical base, the issues of culture were not even considered, and its formation took place in parallel. And therefore, gaining experience in building a corporate structure took place over a long period of time. In modern conditions, when attention to issues of organizational culture has increased, its influence on the effectiveness of activities has been proven, the issue of its formation is gaining formal consolidation. Leading corporations form organizational culture consciously and it must be embedded in the organizational structure.

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